

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN FINANCIAL RISK MANAGEMENT: TRANSFORMING DECISION-MAKING IN BANKING AND CORPORATE FINANCE

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Abstract

As technology continues to evolve, people are constantly seeking new ways to simplify their workflows. It indicates that people are looking for alternative methods to perform duties more efficiently. The advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) has been advantageous to stakeholders, including financial specialists and bankers. For years, financial services have initiated initiatives to develop artificial intelligence (AI) to assist with a diverse array of job responsibilities.

Artificial intelligence looks to be replacing humans in several tasks. It also indicates that the demand for human capital in certain occupations has dropped, which may have negative long-term consequences as the majority of people will remain unemployed. In reality, the concept of financial risk management is where AI truly succeeds. Due to advancements in artificial intelligence, many financial services are now completed with greater speed and efficiency compared to previous methods.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is being used into financial services by financial managers and other stakeholders to improve accuracy of financial outcomes and save time. Artificial intelligence (AI) aids in more informed decision-making, which lowers costs and reduces risk in the financial services sector. Therefore, when used properly, AI may benefit the industry and foster its expansion and advancement.

Keywords: Financial Risk Management, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Decision-making, Finance and Banking.

INTRODUCTION

Although the banking industry has always relied heavily on technology and data, new data-enabled AI technology has the potential to promote innovation more quickly than in the past. AI has the potential to enhance customer experience, manage risk and regulatory requirements, promote differentiation, facilitate expansion, and increase efficiency. By using AI to automate labor-intensive compliance procedures and automatically identify regulatory changes to make sure they stay in compliance, banks can increase efficiency and save money. AI has the power to increase productivity and develop preventative measures that benefit lenders and consumers alike. Banks can gain by using consumer data to anticipate reasons why customers could miss payments, spot warning signs for potential defaults and delinquencies, and provide tailored catch-up solutions. AI is a powerful tool with a wide range of uses in the insurance and banking industries. Applying machine learning (ML) and AI could be very beneficial to the financial services industry. They fundamentally alter the financial services sector and the way that they are offered to clients. It could lead to more knowledgeable and customized goods and services as well as improved cybersecurity, risk reduction, and internal process efficiency (Polireddi, 2024).

The financial services sector is the largest consumer of AI services outside of the technology industry, and it is expanding at an incredibly rapid rate. AI applications in finance have expanded to other industries, including banks, regulators, Fintech, insurance companies, hedge funds and HFT organizations. Many financial services firms are looking into alternatives to fraud prevention based on AI (Buchanan, 2019).

Artificial intelligence (AI) has become one of the most ground-breaking technological innovations in recent years. The field of artificial intelligence has expanded at a rate never seen before due to a greater acceptance of new technological developments, and its applications are currently being investigated in a wide range of commercial sectors. One factor that has been attributed to this expansion is the increased application of recent technology innovations. Artificial intelligence-based systems have the power to not only raise an organization's overall performance but also completely change the financial sector. One of the few industries that has demonstrated a respectable level of artificial intelligence technology adoption and implementation is the financial services sector. Because of this, it is now leading other industries. This is true even though artificial intelligence has been used in a greater variety of industries and businesses than in others (Svoboda, 2024).

In this paper, research method was conducted and the data collection tool was the survey. It is based on the given research questions, which are:

1. How artificial intelligence is used in financial risk management?
2. Why corporate finance's and banking's decision-making transformed by artificial intelligence?

The concept of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

According to Frankfield (2023) the term artificial intelligence (AI) can be used to describe the simulation of human intelligence using heuristics programmed into software. These days, a wide range of applications including cloud-based apps, embedded firmware, enterprise and consumer apps use this code. Businesses

brought artificial intelligence (AI) into the general public at COVID-19 thanks to the app Generative Pre-Training Transformer's popularity and familiarity. Indeed, one of the more well-known AI applications is ChatGPT OpenAI. When most people hear the word artificial intelligence, they immediately think of robots. This is due to the frequent depiction of humanoid robots wreaking devastation on Earth in high-budget books and films.

AI operates under the premise that human intelligence is displayed in a way that robots can readily copy and perform jobs of any complexity. The AI aims to replicate human cognitive function. Because they are concretely portrayed, researchers and programmers are making unexpectedly quick progress in this field of imitation activities including learning, reasoning, and per-

ception. With the advancement of technology, the previous patterns may become outdated and render AI artificial (Frankenfield, 2023).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is used in many different applications nowadays, such as personal assistants and driverless cars. AI appears to be expanding quickly these days, yet in science fiction, AI is sometimes represented as robots, which appear to be more like humans. Artificial Intelligence uses algorithms to find patterns impacted by vast volumes of data. Artificial intelligence (AI) can increase productivity, augment human intelligence, and provide knowledge. AI is seen as a tool that enables people to reconsider how information is integrated and data is processed, then apply the newfound insights to make better decisions. Artificial intelligence systems have long been beneficial for promoting social change and environmental sustainability (Saleh, 2019).

Figure 1: Branches of AI

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332548325_Artificial_Intelligence_Definition_Ethics_and_Standards

The ability to apply and acquire the proper skills to achieve context-appropriate goals and solve issues in a world that is uncertain and continually changing is referred to as intelligence. Fully programmed factory robots are recognized as precise, flexible, and consistent even if they are not thought to be intelligent. A word that was first used in 1955 by John McCarthy, an emeritus professor at Stanford. In order to create sentient devices, he invented science and engineering (Stanford University, 2020).

Due to its rapid evolution, definitions of AI also changed over time. In recent years, stronger definitions of AI that link to intelligent human behavior have been found. In fact, the AI community is already attempting to mimic intelligent behavior through the use of computer programs. Because of this, this isn't thought of as an easy process, which is why computer programs can do a variety of tasks that are referred to as intelligent. In addition to reviewing broad definitions of artificial intelligence, people could restrict their search to accurate descriptions of AI systems (Kok et al, 2021).

According to Rouse (2022) narrow artificial intelligence refers to a specific kind of AI in which the learning algorithm is designed to accomplish a particular task and the information gained from that task is not

automatically applied to other tasks. Mimic sophisticated mental processes for generic AI. Language translation and image recognition are two notable uses of AI. Narrow AI includes well-known AI applications that have been used recently. Indeed, weak AI is the colloquial term for narrow AI. Recommendation engines and other types of narrow AI power the majority of commercial apps. As learning algorithms become more complex, narrow AI applications become more complex.

In its strictest sense, artificial intelligence (AI) refers to machines that mimic human intelligence. Since many of the apps available today are actually rather simplistic, they are not true artificial intelligence. As a result, the definitions that are provided also become improper for reporting; the deployment of this suggests that artificial intelligence does not yet exist. Artificial Intelligence is a generally accepted technology that enables machines to simulate sophisticated human abilities. AI could also be defined as machines that do complicated tasks in complex situations. In reality, other definitions might go farther in explaining these abilities and activities (Sheikh, Prins & Schrijvers, 2023).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is considered a subfield of computer science (CS), which is the scientific study

of providing answers for various issues, learning precisely which jobs should be handled, and including elements that allow learning machine languages. Additionally, algorithms are offered to show different concerns in a practical, efficient, moral, and physical manner. Artificial intelligence (AI) is developed as computer science and engineering advance, which sets boundaries for particular programs. Computational psychology, which is devoted to written programs as models or theories connected to human cognitive behavior, is actually a component of artificial intelligence (Rapaport, 2019).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming widely used in today's world and has a lot of consequences on industries and society as a whole, thus it should not be undervalued. Studying AI research is essential for a number of reasons. AI is changing a lot of businesses, and there is a real need for experts in the field who have the necessary knowledge and abilities (Fernandes, 2023).

The importance of artificial intelligence and its related components has long been acknowledged. They were considered methods and instruments to improve our world for many years. Although these technologies are still designed to minimize human labor, they are nevertheless considered as tremendous human assets. They typically involve the capacity to function well in automated ways. Therefore, when it comes to managing components related to this AI technology, manual involvement is seen as the last resort (Pedamkar, 2023).

According to Pothens (2022) the biggest successes of AI are reported to be a decrease in human error. In contrast to people, computing devices cannot make mistakes if they are correctly programmed; on the other hand, humans may occasionally make mistakes. Thus, AI applies predefined sets of algorithms, reduces error probability, gathers stored data, and improves task accuracy and precision. The nicest thing about AI is that it can help with complex problems that require challenging calculations and that can be handled error-free. Additionally, this AI records numerous major benefits in numerous fields.

Doctors can more easily and accurately anticipate serious health concerns like cancer at an early stage by using advanced AI-based technology. People these days are completely dependent on their smartphones and the Internet for their everyday needs. One well-known instance of digital help offered is chatbot support, which can be found on a number of websites. Users make inquiries on certain topics, and computer systems enable the delivery of pre-given information on topics including banking, travel, education, and ticketing. Certain chatbots are designed in a way that makes it difficult for humans or chatbots to understand them (Pothens, 2022).

As reported by Accenture (2022) Science and popular culture believe that artificial intelligence (AI) will transform commerce and the way that technologies and people interact with one another. Artificial intelligence usage is improving more quickly than ever before due to the maturity of advances in processing power, cloud computing, and data proliferation. Businesses now have access to previously unheard-of esoteric data that

was previously unknown to them. Businesses that scale well see higher returns on their AI investments. Unsurprisingly, senior executives think that using AI will help them achieve their growth objectives. AI is unsure about how labor-intensive tasks might be improved upon and made more efficient. Scalable AI typically becomes a survival pillar and is one of the primary enablers for establishing strategic priorities.

The majority of businesses use artificial intelligence (AI) primarily in the Internet of Things and massive volumes of collected data to inform marketing campaigns, enhance operational efficiency, and provide better customer service. In fact, artificial intelligence (AI) helps businesses of all shapes and sizes in all relevant industries increase profits and productivity at all business stages in the lifecycle, from sourcing materials to accounting and from sales to providing customer service. This starts with supply chains being managed globally, which leads to supply routes being optimized. AI is also used to enhance lives. In general, using AI to create creative compositions—from music to books, to developing recipes based on what's currently in the cupboard—and even to produce works of art increases the impact of AI on everyday life (Marr, 2022).

As said by Pratt (2023) Artificial intelligence (AI) generates predictions based on training data and algorithms supplied by AI developers. Machine learning algorithms aid in machine learning promptly, but they do not possess human creativity. Instead, they require novel approaches to inspiration and thought. Though it's still up for debate, research primarily indicates that artificial intelligence (AI) is being created to increase the likelihood that it will be able to reason like humans.

Some AI users have reported using the system without verifying the results because they believe it to be error-free, but in practice, there are occasionally issues. Actually, records of malfunctioning AI systems suggest that AI is still far from ideal (Bhosale, Pujari & Multani, 2020).

According to Sultan (2021) the rising automation of AI has resulted in the loss of over 300 million jobs worldwide. The majority of wealthy nations, which have implemented powerful AI, run the risk of seeing the greatest job losses. Therefore, academics and economics recommend developing new employment categories that are unaffected by AI advancements. Employees need acquire new skills to supplement their human abilities in order to fully deploy AI. AI automation has a significant impact on some businesses while having a partial impact on others (Sultan, 2021).

Based on Rafi (2022) AI in the workplace has the potential to damage interpersonal connections since there is obviously no connection between humans and machines. Since AI is always evolving, hardware and software ought to be current with the most recent features. Machines need maintenance and repairs on a regular basis, which can be costly. AI apps and systems seem like complicated machinery, therefore developing them costs a lot of money.

Analysis of financial risk management influenced by artificial intelligence

According to Arevalo (2021) financial risk is defined as the potential loss of capital associated with an enterprise or investment. Liquidity risk, credit risk, and operational risk are a few of the most notable and prevalent financial hazards. In actuality, financial risk is recognized as a kind of danger that results in the capital of interested parties being lost. This means that governments are unable to pay back bonds or handle other financial problems. Companies with outstanding debts also run the risk of defaulting, although doing so could put a strain on their finances and lead to company failures.

Financial risk is defined as the potential for governments to become incapable of effectively managing their monetary policies and to be reluctant or unable to control inflation and defaults on bonds or other debt problems. People who make poor decisions run the danger of losing money. This risk arises for a number of reasons, such as making extremely risky investments or taking an unneeded day off. Some efforts are made without fully understanding the implications, even when they involve risks and dangers that are possibly unmanageable. Financial risk exists to varying degrees and is neither intrinsically good nor negative (Blach, 2010).

Based on Abeyrathna and Kalainathan (2016) the likelihood of losing money as a result of making the incorrect trading or investing decision is referred to as financial risk. People or businesses that take financial risks lose capital. Financial hazards come in a variety of forms, including credit risk and operational risk. As

a matter of fact, financial risk is regarded as a threat to capital. This suggests that there could be a financial loss. The inadequacy of firms' cash flows to fulfill their obligations poses a financial risk. Known financial risks include those related to investments, law, etc.

The position of wasting money due to unfavorable trading and investment results is referred to as financial risk. Threats come in many different forms. Certain hazards can be readily managed, while others are uncontrollable. Businesses incur financial risks in order to prepare themselves for growth and new opportunities. The financial risk increases with the amount of debt an organization has. Any person or business considering investing should be made aware of the many financial risks, such as currency risk, and how to reduce them through strategies like hedging (Anjaneyulu, 2022).

The danger that businesses won't be able to pay their debts in full is known as financial risk. It is true that investors in the businesses could lose the money they put in. When deciding whether to invest in a certain business, financial risk is recognized as a factor to take into account. In actuality, financial risk indicators help investors reduce risk. One type of risk that arises from events and affects people's financial circumstances is referred to as financial risk. Nothing in this life is risk-free, especially when it comes to money. Financial stability can be threatened by a number of different issues, or it can be disturbed by them. However, overcoming financial risk does not require its happening. Businesses can take certain actions to reduce their financial risk (Gabriel & Baker, 1980).

Figure 2: Financial risk types

Source: <https://www.simplilearn.com/financial-risk-and-types-rar131-article>

The iterative process of risk management consists of identifying risks, measuring them, and putting plans in place to reduce them to manageable levels. In actuality, financial risk management is regarded as an efficient method used in businesses to control financial risks in order to stop income leaks. The difficulty of

regulatory compliance has significantly increased as a result. If competent compliance managers handle risk management, compliance becomes simpler. Automation of the compliance ecosystem facilitates easier tracking of regulatory compliance (Duyvendijk, 2022).

Benefits of financial risk management

Lowering costs of bankruptcy
Reducing taxable income volatility
Lowering weighted average cost of capital
Reducing diversifiable risk
Improving management incentives
Lowering probability of debt overhang
Reducing information asymmetries

Source: <https://www.simplilearn.com/reducing-information-asymmetries-article>

Benefits of financial risk management are shown in Table 1 and include lowering information asymmetries, lowering the likelihood of a debt overhang, lowering diversifiable risk, and more.

Best practices for financial risk management (FRM) provide businesses with ways to deal with the most unsettling financial risks and reduce, eliminate, or lessen their impact or possibility. After managing a range of specified risks, businesses in a turbulent market gain an advantage with regular risk assessments and a financial risk management method (Lancaster & Goff, 2021).

According to Kiseleva (2018) there has been an increase in interest in efficient risk identification and, more importantly, risk identification management as a result of recent setbacks experienced by both public and private sector businesses worldwide. Most businesses submit reports on a regular basis to regulatory bodies detailing their risk management procedures. However, it discovered that these recurring reports to management bodies are insufficient to successfully reduce risks.

AI-powered risk prediction algorithms support proactive risk management techniques by giving real-time insights into possible financial hazards. Artificial intelligence integration presents benefits as well as obstacles in the field of financial risk management. The difficulty of integrating AI into risk management procedures, the requirement to get beyond cultural barriers, and the moral implications of AI applications are some of the difficulties. On the other hand, there are plenty of prospects, from the possibility of improved decision-making to the development of creative approaches to risk mitigation (Leitner et al., 2024).

Artificial Intelligence has wide-ranging applications in financial risk management. For example, machine learning algorithms are capable of effectively assessing credit risk by analyzing large volumes of historical data. Artificial intelligence (AI)-driven fraud detection systems can spot trends and abnormalities instantly, reducing monetary losses. AI-driven algorithms that process massive information and produce predicted insights are beneficial for market risk monitoring. The automation and effectiveness of AI-driven solutions can help enhance operational risk management and regulatory compliance (Siddiqui, 2023).

Transforming decision-making in corporate finance and banking due to artificial intelligence

Businesses are facing increased pressure to modify their systems and procedures in order to increase efficiency and save expenses as more individuals live digital lives. At the vanguard of this revolution is the

financial services sector, and specifically the banking industry, which is utilizing cutting-edge technology like artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to cut down on fraud, create new efficiencies, and improve customer service. Large volumes of data are commonly used in the financial services industry; these volumes have increased dramatically in recent years and are predicted to continue rising in the years to come. Globally, society is predicted to generate 463 exabytes of data each day by 2025, with each human being estimated to have created at least 1.7 MB of data per second on average in 2020. Banks may leverage the insights found in these massive, complicated data sets to enhance decision-making, create risk models that are more accurate, and spot suspicious behavior or transactions in real time. But humans are not equipped to accurately examine this volume of data on their own. Because of this, banks are using technology to efficiently handle enormous volumes of data and find important insights that can enhance customer satisfaction, lower risk, and improve decision-making (Valleskey, 2024).

The financial industry is entering a new era of data-driven decision-making, efficiency, security, and customer experience with the introduction of AI. Artificial Intelligence is driving the operations of financial institutions and startups. AI algorithms are using real-time market data to execute tasks at previously unheard-of speeds and accuracy. This allows them to gain profound insights and prescribe investment plans. AI is providing cutting-edge solutions that improve customer satisfaction, operational effectiveness, and decision-making. The way financial institutions function in the contemporary world is being redefined by this shift towards a more data-driven and technologically sophisticated approach (Layn, 2024).

AI is transforming the banking industry by automating repetitive processes and supplying sophisticated insights for decision-making. AI is revolutionizing customer interaction with tailored experiences and advanced risk management, in addition to increasing efficiency. Applying machine learning techniques, data analytics, and computational logic to financial services is what artificial intelligence (AI) in baking is all about. It is applied to improve decision-making, customer service, and operational efficiency. Banking AI reduces effort required to make inquiries, saves time for users, and enhances service ease. Chatbots with AI capabilities that have been trained on large datasets can offer financial management support and guidance to their clients. Chatbots with AI capabilities can be used by users to streamline financial transactions (Kryvenets, 2024).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a game-changing catalyst in corporate finance, transforming conventional approaches and promoting efficiency and well-informed decision-making. Businesses may overcome traditional constraints with AI, creating new opportunities for expansion, risk mitigation, and value creation. AI offers a wide range of tools that are changing the corporate finance landscape, from prescriptive modeling to predictive analytics. Intelligent decision-making in corporate finance is made possible in large part by machine learning, a crucial aspect of artificial intelligence (Rane, Choudhary & Rane, 2024). Artificial Intelligence (AI) is causing a rapid transition in the financial sector, opening up new opportunities, and changing conventional procedures. Financial institutions that want to remain competitive in a market that is changing quickly must embrace artificial intelligence (AI) as a strategic necessity rather than just a technological advancement. Enhancing the client experience

is one of AI's most important effects in banking. Financial institutions may provide their consumers with more individualized and responsive services thanks to chatbots and virtual assistants driven by AI. These AI-powered solutions can respond to client inquiries, give round-the-clock assistance, and even provide personalized financial guidance. Customers gain from increased service effectiveness and quality as a result, which raises customer satisfaction and loyalty rates. AI is also transforming risk management in the banking industry (Douglas, 2024).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to choose these respondents with specific vocations, purposeful sampling was utilized. There were 77 samples in total that took part in the survey. People who took part in the survey are displayed in the tables below.

Table 2

Respondents' sexes and ages

Ages	Numbers of respondents	Sexes	Numbers of respondents
Ranging 25 – 32 years	44	Males	51
Ranging 33 – 40 years	27	Females	26
Ranging 41 – 48 years	6	Mix	

Source: own elaboration

Table 3

Respondents' education backgrounds and occupations

Occupations	Numbers of respondents	Education backgrounds	Numbers of respondents
AI experts	18	Masters' titles	60
Financial analysts	33	Bachelor's titles	8
Bankers	26	Other education levels	9

Source: own elaboration

Table 4

Respondents' marital status

Marital status	Numbers of respondents
Singles	25
With marriages	49
Other relationship	3

Source: own elaboration

Table 5

Survey questions

Nr#	Given survey questions
1	Why is artificial intelligence given consideration?
2	Which financial domains does AI apply to?
3	How do you rate the use of AI in financial services industry?
4	Do banks and corporate finance live up to AI's expectations?
5	What difficulties does the financial services?

Source: own elaboration

Data collection procedure

There are a number of situations where doing research studies is necessary. Scholars propose carrying out investigations to obtain fresh perspectives and understanding regarding the assigned study tasks. Research studies are necessary in the cases of financial risk management and artificial intelligence. For this

project, primary data on the subject of artificial intelligence in the financial services sector is gathered using the quantitative research methodology. This study, which focuses on artificial intelligence in the financial services business, is actually conducted in-depth. In reality, the survey method is the name given to the data collection tool in this work.

Purposively sampling is used to collect respondents for the survey. The respondents of this study varied in terms of age, gender, and occupation. These responders communicated in person.

Research limitations

During the survey-taking procedure, a number of constraints were observed. Bias may exist if there are few responders relative to the total number of respondents. Having responses that represent a variety of viewpoints and racial backgrounds could help lessen this bias. The results could be skewed in the companies' favor due to this bias. To overcome these limitations, a mixed method approach that takes into account a wider range of industries and cultural contexts can be used. Actually, because sample size guarantees dependability and validity, it has a big influence on the outcomes.

Moreover, since this method relies on online participation to gather data, conversations frequently stray from the study's primary focus.

Labor-intensive approach: the classification, data security, and efficacy of the data analysis made this a labor-intensive procedure. This limitation can be managed by classifying tasks. The method is inadequate in

several measurements or indicators when it comes to evaluating how Accounting Information Systems and financial analysis affect strategic financial management. A survey-only method might not allow for the exploration of unexpected finds. Incorporating additional research methods is also suggested to manage this constraint and generate more comprehensive data for the future investigation.

Research instrument

Purposive sampling was taken into consideration for the survey, which made it easier to choose at least 77 respondents on purpose. Following the online survey's release to the chosen respondents on their social media accounts, the replies were carefully chosen to ensure that they came from respondents with experience in artificial intelligence and finance as well as specific fields whose responses would ultimately be examined for the study.

RESULTS

In this section, research findings are presented which are as follows:

Theoretical contribution

It is anticipated that this study will offer insightful information about artificial intelligence's experiences and perceptions in the financial services sector and financial risk management. Additionally, it broadens understanding of two topics: (1) banks and corporate finance; and (2) financial services utilized by stakeholders, businesses, and individuals. Policy makers and financial risk managers who are interested in enhancing finance will find the findings to be helpful in providing suggestions.

Furthermore, this study will add to the more general conversations about the potential for employing artificial intelligence to prevent fraud and provide efficient financial services.

CONCLUSION

In order to maintain banks' stability and profitability, effective risk management is essential. It supports investor confidence, ensures regulatory compliance, and protects assets. Negligent risk management can result in substantial monetary losses, legal repercussions, and harm to one's reputation. AI integration has the potential to improve risk management procedures' predictive, efficient, and accurate capacities.

The quick development of AI has given it previously unheard-of capabilities, which begs the question of how well-suited humans are to these advancements in finance. AI has developed into a potent instrument for the banking and financial industries, assisting them in streamlining their processes and providing clients with individualized services. It has already demonstrated the ability to change how we perceive banking, evaluate risks, and spot dishonest behavior. AI has made fraud detection and risk assessment much simpler and more efficient. AI algorithms are capable of sifting through enormous volumes of data to find anomalies that could indicate fraud before it occurs. Similarly, AI models are used in the lending industry to examine a wide range of data, including non-traditional sources, in order to more accurately anticipate loan recipients and lower the number of defaults.

Applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in banking and finance combine several forms of smart technology to identify, assess, and efficiently reduce risks, hence improving the efficiency of banking and financial operations. AI is a major factor in reducing risk in banking and finance. Banks can limit risks and make more intelligent decisions when AI is used for risk management. There are many potential and difficult obstacles to overcome in the banking industry when integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into risk management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations that follow will be provided in this work in the following manner:

- Millions of US dollars should be invested in various AI tools and systems to accomplish tasks;
- Financial managers and other experts in the field of finance should develop their AI knowledge to fulfill different works;
- Financial institutions should hire more AI experts to ensure that all processes are fulfilled with AI systems.

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